

were followed. We recorded yield at 14% moisture level.

The regression of genotypes for average yield on the environmental index resulted in regression coefficients (b) ranging from -0.1677 to 2.0643 (see table). The coefficient of determination (r^2) ranged from 0.0224 to 0.9529. The deviation from regression mean squares

($S^2 d$), a true measure of genotypic stability, ranged from 0.0223 to 0.7997.

PK3717-9, PK3727-2, PK3717-12, PK3727-5, PK3849-18, and KS282 showed higher yields than the pooled means, but they had varied responses to environmental fluctuations. PK3727-2 and PK3727-5 were unstable for yield because of the significant values of b_i and $S^2 d$.

PK3717-9, PK3717-12, and PK3849-18 yielded higher than the pooled mean. These genotypes also showed non-significant values for b_i and $S^2 d$, indicating stable genotype interaction over three environments. They can be recommended for use in breeding programs aiming to develop cultivars with high yield potential and better adaptability. □

Genetic studies for allogamous traits in *oryza sativa* L.

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We studied the nature of the gene action of two traits—anther length and pollen grain size—in F_1 from a diallel cross involving the rice varieties and lines Basmati 370, Basmati 385, Basmati 198, and 4048.

We laid out the experiment during 1991 kharif in a randomized complete block design, with three replications, and a spacing of 30 cm between rows and plants. We measured anther length and pollen grain size using a binocular microscope and recorded 10 observations for both traits from each of the main panicles of 10 plants per replication for each genotype.

The components of variation (see table) revealed that additive component (D) exceeded the dominance components H_1 and H_2 for anther length, indicating additive type of gene action for increased anther length. The inverse, however, was true for pollen grain size. Recessive

Estimates of components of variation with their standard errors for anther length and pollen grain size in rice.

Anther length (mm)	Pollen grain size (μ)
$D \pm SE (D) = 0.0236 \pm 3.1623$	1.2795 ± 1.2669
$F \pm SE (F) = -0.0197 \pm 8.124$	1.3540 ± 3.2546
$H_1 \pm SE (H_1) = 0.0155 \pm 9.1924$	10.2192 ± 3.6826
$H_2 \pm SE (H_2) = 0.0090 \pm 8.4853$	8.0473 ± 3.3993
$h^2 \pm SE (h) = 4.0015 \pm 5.8310$	4.5319 ± 2.3305
$E \pm SE (E) = 0.002 \pm 0.4142$	0.727 ± 0.5666
Derived values	
$\sqrt{H_1/D}$	$= 0.8102 \quad 2.8261$
$H_2/4H_1$	$= 0.1457 \quad 0.1969$
$[\{4DH\}^{1/2} + F]/[\{4DH\}^{1/2} - F]$	$= 0.32 \quad 1.512$
h^2/H	$= -0.163 \quad 0.563$

alleles were important for anther length whereas more dominant alleles were observed for pollen grain size in parent varieties. H_1 and H_2 were not similar in both traits, showing that positive and negative allele frequencies were unequal.

The mean degree of dominance, 0.81 and 2.83, indicated partial dominance for anther length and overdominance for pollen grain size. The ratio of H_2 to $4H_1$

(0.14, 0.20) showed unequal positive and negative allele frequencies for both traits. The ratio h^2 to H_2 indicated that no dominant gene was controlling anther length whereas at least one gene controlling pollen grain size exhibited some dominance. This information will be useful in designing future hybrid rice breeding programs. □

Inheritance of aroma in two aromatic rice varieties

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Jin-Long Dao and 80-66 are two later maturing aromatic rice varieties developed by HRRRI. We made reciprocal

crosses between these scented varieties and nonscented rice varieties HA8857 and Xiang Zao Xian no. 1 and 3 in 1989 to study aroma inheritance.

We sowed the F_1 and F_2 progeny and the parents from these crosses in Apr 1990 and transplanted them in May 1990. Thirty plants of each parent, 30 F_1 plants from each reciprocal cross, and about 200 F_2 plants of each cross from the four

Scent ratings of F_1 , F_2 , and parents, HRRRI, Changsha, China, 1990.

Entry	Plants (no.)			χ^2 (3:1)	P
	Total	Nonscented	Scented		
Parent					
Jin-Long Dao	30	0	30		
80-66	30	0	30		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
HA8557	30	30	0		
F_1					
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
Jin-Long Dao/HA8557	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
HA8557/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
80-66/HA8557	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1/80-66	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3/80-66	30	30	0		
HA8557/80-66	30	30	0		
F_2					
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	186	143	43	0.2580	0.50-0.75
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	160	124	36	0.4083	0.50-0.75
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	142	105	37	0.0375	>0.90
80-66/HA8557	161	124	37	0.4083	0.50-0.75

crosses were evaluated. We placed 2-g leaf blades from each plant in 10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution according to the method of Sood and Siddiq. Samples

were smelled and evaluated for aroma after 10 min.

F₁ plants from all the reciprocal crosses were nonaromatic, indicating that

a recessive nuclear gene controls aroma in Jin-Long Dao and 80-66. The F₂ plant scent evaluation indicated a 3:1 (non-aroma:aroma) segregation (see table). □

Breeding methods

Heterosis and inbreeding depression in rice

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Ten divergent parents—Mahsuri, Adamchini, IET4140, IET7562, Kanakjeera, IR50, IR52, Dhaneswar, Pawanpeer, and TAU18—were crossed in all possible combinations, excluding reciprocals, to study the extent of heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and inbreeding depression for yield and yield components.

Parents and their 45 F₁ and 45 F₂ were grown in a completely randomized block design, with three replications. Plants were spaced at 20 × 15 cm, with one row of 20 plants for parents and F₁ and six rows of 20 plants for F₂. Observations were recorded for 10 randomly selected plants from parents and F₁, and 50 plants from F₂.

The genotypic correlation coefficient indicated that grain yield was positively and significantly correlated with number of effective tillers/plant ($r = 0.38$) and number of grains/panicle ($r = 0.45$). Other characters, such as days to panicle emergence, plant height, panicle length, and 100-grain weight, showed either negative or nonsignificant positive correlations with yield.

The cross combinations exhibiting more than 20% heterobeltiosis for grain yield are in the table. Crosses showing more than 40% heterobeltiosis for grain yield were Kanakjeer/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET4140/TAU 18, Adamchini/TAU 18, Adamchini/Pawanpeer, Adamchini/IET7562, and Adamchini/IR50. Crosses showing better negative heterobeltiosis for days to panicle emergence were Adamchini/IET7562 and Adamchini/IR50, IET7562/IR52; for plant height, they were Adamchini/IET7562, Adamchini/Pawanpeer, Adamchini/IR50, IET4140/TAU18, and Kanakjeera/IR52.

Only 11 of 54 crosses showed positive significant heterobeltiosis for number of effective tillers/plant. Crosses with appreciable heterobeltiosis were Mahsuri/Kanakjeera, IET4140/IR52, and IR50/Pawanpeer.

The crosses with high heterobeltiosis for grains/panicle were IET4140/TAU 18, IET4140/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET7562/IR52, IET4140/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET7562/IR52, and IET7562/TAU18. The crosses Mahsuri/IET4140 and IET7562/IR50 expressed better heterobeltiosis for 100-grain weight.

Out of 45 crosses, 31 showed significant inbreeding depression for plant height, 32 for days to panicle emergence, 41 for panicle length, 42 for tillers/plant, 31 for grains/panicle, 41 for 100-grain weight, and 42 for grain yield. Some crosses had high heterosis with high inbreeding depression, some showed more heterosis and medium inbreeding depression, and some had high heterosis with low inbreeding depression. □

Heterobeltiosis and inbreeding depression for yield and its components in promising hybrids. ^a

Cross	Days to panicle emergence		Plant height (cm)		Effective tillers/plant (no.)		Grains/panicle (no.)		Grain yield/plant	
	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)
Mahsuri/IET7562	-14.5**	-6.3**	3.9**	1.0	-9.0	20.2**	-30.7**	30.4**	34.9**	50.8**
Mahsuri/Kanakjeera	0.1	5.4**	3.8**	13.6**	31.6**	41.1**	-36.7**	26.2**	44.7**	61.7**
Mahsuri/Pawanpeer	-4.3**	13.9**	-1.9	-9.8**	11.3**	49.9**	-36.8**	35.5**	34.3**	56.6**
Mahsuri/TAU18	-7.0**	-2.8*	-2.1	8.8**	-6.5	23.0**	-19.9**	32.8**	20.7**	38.3**
Adamchini/IET7562	-24.6**	-11.9**	-27.7**	-9.2**	-19.0**	32.6**	14.9**	34.0**	54.6**	55.5**
Adamchini/IR50	-17.3**	4.7**	-13.6**	4.4**	-9.3	0.4	-11.2**	2.1	45.0**	22.2**
Adamchini/Pawanpeer	-10.5**	5.7**	-22.7**	15.3**	0.2	18.3**	-40.0**	9.1**	57.4**	17.6**
Adamchini/TAU18	-6.9**	5.3**	7.6**	7.4**	13.4**	26.8**	-9.2**	6.9**	57.5**	28.4**
IET4140/Kanakjeera	-0.1	3.1	-12.9**	9.1**	-5.6	17.1**	38.2**	-52.4**	28.4**	20.9**
IET4140/IR50	4.0**	11.5**	-2.8*	-30.3**	-42.3**	0.5	46.0**	11.3**	41.7**	13.3**
IET4140/IR52	14.1**	5.0**	1.4	10.0**	33.1**	11.1**	-6.4**	8.4**	20.7**	39.7**
IET4140/Pawanpeer	-0.2	2.4*	2.7	12.2**	12.5**	26.1**	14.9**	4.1*	20.4**	15.0**
IET4140/TAU18	0.8	1.4	-15.5**	2.6	2.7	10.7	52.1**	21.4**	70.4**	23.7**
IET7562/Pawanpeer	0.2	2.0	19.0**	1.5	-3.3	31.0**	3.1*	16.3**	34.0**	55.9**
Kanakjeera/IR50	2.2*	6.2**	-1.4	19.6**	-14.9**	18.8**	-15.5**	7.5**	160.4**	50.4**
Kanakjeera/TAU18	3.9**	3.8**	6.4**	6.1	-17.2**	5.2	17.2**	28.6**	33.8**	37.2**
IR50/Pawanpeer	-0.7	7.7**	24.5**	11.6**	22.8**	29.8**	61.3**	44.7**	98.7**	61.1**
IR50/TAU18	-4.1**	-1.5	-15.1**	-3.0*	-1.3	33.7**	-3.2*	5.2**	24.1**	16.3**
Pawanpeer/TAU18	7.3**	6.4**	-5.7**	10.2**	-10.5	13.4*	-0.0	6.2**	35.2**	29.8**
SE	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.5	0.6	0.4	2.4	2.5	1.1	0.8

^a * = significance at P = 5%. ** = significance at P = 1%. HBT = heterobeltiosis, ID = inbreeding depression

Zinc increases rate of twin seedlings of rice

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We studied how Zn affected the rate of twin seedlings in polyembryonic rice varieties: *indica* Shuang 3 and Shuang 13, and *japonica* Lu 52.

Three hundred dehulled seeds per treatment were soaked in different concentrations of Zn²⁺ (ZnSO₄) solution at 37°C for 1 d. The check was soaked in distilled water. The seeds were then sterilized in 0.1% mercuric chloride for 10 min and placed in the same solution at 25°C to hasten germination. Twin seedling rates were calculated 4 d later.